

Social

A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary students. The investigator adopted survey method to study the social intelligence between students from selected government, private and aided school. For this study a sample of 300 school students from eight various schools which are situated in Palakkad district selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique. The findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement. This study shows that students do not find healthy environment in schools for developing their social intelligence. The schools fail to provide a proper environment to develop better relationship, positive behavior, social skills positive attitudes and good mental health in students.

Keywords: Social Intelligence; Academic Achievement.

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1. Introduction

Socially intelligent people are more probable to flourish in everything they undertake in their life. Contrasting what is demanded to I.Q one can learn and improve some vital social capabilities, flagging the way for growing their social intelligence and thus creating their life more healthy, enjoyable, successful and satisfied in the upcoming days. The concept of social intelligence is to be highly praised, not because it is new but because it seizes the essence of work. The present investigation is an attempt to study the relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement of the higher secondary school students from selected government,

aided and private schools located in Palakkad district. The findings of the study help to discover the social intelligence and relationship with academic achievement in English.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

- To find the relation between social intelligence and academic achievement in English among higher secondary school students.
- To adopt questionnaire on social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

- To find out the social intelligence among higher secondary school students.
- To find out the achievement in English among higher secondary school students.
- To find out the impact of personal variables like Medium of Instruction, Gender, Location of the School, Type of the School, Educational qualification of father, Educational qualification of mother, Occupation of Father, Occupation of Mother on social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study the social intelligence and academic achievement in English among higher secondary school students. For the study about social intelligence and academic achievement in English, the sample size is 300 higher secondary students from 8 various schools which are situated in and around Palakkad district in Kerala.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Medium of Instruction	Malayalam	159	53%	300
		English	141	47%	
2.	Gender	Male	150	50%	300
		Female	150	50%	
3.	Location of the School	Urban	150	50%	300
		Rural	150	50%	
4.	Type of the School	Govt.	98	32.7%	300
		Aided	111	37%	
		Private	91	30.3%	
5.	Educational Qualification of father	Below 10 th	53	17.7%	300
		UG	134	44.7%	
		PG	57	19%	
		Professional	56	18.7%	

6.	Educational Qualification of mother	Below 10 th	65	21.7%	300
		UG	122	40.7%	
		PG	56	18.7%	
		Professional	57	19%	
7.	Occupation of Father	Daily Wagers	44	14.7%	300
		Farmer	89	29.7%	
		Govt.Job	65	21.7%	
		Private	44	14.7%	
		Business	58	19.3%	
8.	Occupation of Mother	Daily Wagers	55	18.3%	300
		Farmer	65	21.7%	
		Govt.Job	44	14.7%	
		Private	25	8.3%	
		Business	13	4.3%	
		Home maker	98	32.7%	

Table 2: Scoring of Each item

S.No	Dimension	Question no.	Scoring		
			Yes	No	Sometimes
1.	Social Intelligence Scale	1 to 15	3	1	2
2.	Academic Achievement in English (for Positive Questions)	1 to 5, 7,11, 12, 14, 15	3	1	2
3.	Academic Achievement in English (for Negative Questions)	6,8,9,10,13	1	3	2

Table 3: Ranks assigned for the Social Intelligence Scale

Social Intelligence Scale	
Scores	Rank
15 to 25	Low
26 to 35	Moderate
36 to 45	High

Table 4: Ranks assigned for the Academic Achievement in English scores

Academic Achievement in English Scores	
Scores	Rank
15 to 25	Low
26 to 35	Moderate
36 to 45	High

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social intelligence between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Table 5: Frequency and percentage difference towards social intelligence between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Malayalam	1	0.62	36	22.64	122	76.73	159
English	2	1.42	30	21.28	109	77.30	141

From the table 5 that amid the malayalam medium, 76.73% of them have high Level, 22.64% of them have moderate Level and 0.62% of them have low level of social intelligence. Similarly, amid the English medium, 77.30% of them have high Level, 21.05% of them have moderate Level and 1.42% of them have low level of social intelligence.

Table 6: ‘t’ values towards social intelligence between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Medium of Instruction	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Malayalam	159	2.76	0.44	300	0.73	0.23	Not significant
English	141	2.75	0.46				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 6 the calculated value (0.73) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards social intelligence between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards achievement in English between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Table 7: Frequency and percentage difference towards achievement in English between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Malayalam	23	14.47	136	85.53	0	0	159
English	20	14.18	121	85.82	0	0	141

From the table 7 that amid the malayalam medium, 85.53% of them have moderate Level and 14.47% of them have low level of achievement in English. Similarly, amid the English medium, 85.82% of them have moderate Level and 14.18% of them have low level of achievement in English.

Table 8: ‘t’ values towards achievement in English between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

Medium of Instruction	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Malayalam	159	1.855	0.352	300	3.18	0.0008	Significant
English	141	1.858	0.350				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 8 the calculated value (3.18) is greater than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference towards achievement in English between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social intelligence between gender among higher secondary school students.

Table 9: Frequency and percentage difference towards social intelligence between gender among higher secondary school students.

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	3	2	30	20	117	78	150
Female	0	0	36	24	114	76	150

From the table 9 that amid the male students, 78% of them have high Level and 20% of them have low level in Social intelligence. Similarly, amid the female students, 76% of them have high Level and 24% of them have low level in social intelligence.

Table 10: ‘t’ values towards social intelligence between gender among higher secondary school students.

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Male	150	2.76	0.473	300	0.93	0.17	Not significant
Female	150	2.76	0.428				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 10 the calculated value (0.93) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards social intelligence between gender among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 4:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards achievement in English between gender among higher secondary school students.

Table 11: Frequency and percentage difference towards achievement in English between gender among higher secondary school students.

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	23	15.33	127	84.67	0	0	150
Female	20	13.33	130	86.67	0	0	150

From the table 11 that amid the male students, 84.67% of them have moderate level and 15.33% of them have low level in achievement in English. Similarly, amid the female students, 86.67% of them have moderate Level and 13.33% of them have low level in achievement in English.

Table 12: ‘t’ values towards achievement in English between gender among higher secondary school students.

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Male	150	1.846	0.361	300	10.239	0.00001	Significant
Female	150	1.866	0.341				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 12 the calculated value (10.239) is greater than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference towards achievement in English between gender among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 5:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social intelligence between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Table 13: Frequency and percentage difference towards social intelligence between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Location of School	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Urban	2	1.33	34	22.67	114	76	150
Rural	1	0.67	32	21.33	117	78	150

From the table 13 that amid the urban school students, 76% of them have high level, 22.67% of them have moderate level and 1.33% of them have low level in social intelligence. Similarly,

amid the rural school students, 78% of them have high level, 21.33% of them have moderate Level and 0.67% of them have low level in social intelligence.

Table 14: 't' values towards social intelligence between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Location of the School	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Urban	150	2.74	0.46	300	0.80	0.21	Not Significant
Rural	150	2.77	0.43				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.64)

From the table 14 the calculated value (0.80) is less than the table value of 't' (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards social intelligence between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 6:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards achievement in English between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Table 15: Frequency and percentage difference towards achievement in English between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Location of School	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Urban	18	12	132	88	0	0	150
Rural	25	16.67	125	83.33	0	0	150

From the table 15 that amid the urban school students, 88% of them have moderate level and 12% of them have low level in achievement in English. Similarly, amid the rural school students, 83.33% of them have moderate Level and 16.67% of them have low level in achievement in English.

Table 16: 't' values towards achievement in English between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

Location of the School	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Urban	150	2.06	0.10	300	0.87	0.192	Not Significant
Rural	150	2.05	0.11				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.64)

From the table 16 the calculated value (0.87) is less than the table value of 't' (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference

towards achievement in English between location of the school among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 7:

There will be a significant difference towards social intelligence between the types of school among higher secondary school students.

Table 17: Means score difference towards social intelligence between the types of school among higher secondary school students.

Variable	Type of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Government	98	2.78	0.436
	Aided	111	2.79	0.407
	Private School	91	2.69	0.509
	Total	300	2.76	0.450

The table 17 concluded that the mean value of government school is 2.78 whereas the mean value of aided school students is 2.79, the mean value of private school students is 2.69. The result inferred that the mean value for aided school students is better than others.

Table: 18: F-ratio towards social intelligence between the types of school among higher secondary school students.

Source of variance	df	Sum square	Mean square	F	Remarks
Between Group	2	0.601	0.301	1.49	Not Significant
With in group	297	60.119	0.202		

The table 18 concluded that the calculated value of “F” (1.49) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 3.04, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards social intelligence between the types of school among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 8:

There will be a significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of father among higher secondary school students.

Table 19: Means score difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of father among higher secondary school students.

Variable	Educational Qualification of father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Below 10 th	53	3.00	0.00
	UG	134	2.72	0.44
	PG	57	2.77	0.42

Variable	Educational Qualification of father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Below 10 th	53	3.00	0.00
	UG	134	2.72	0.44
	PG	57	2.77	0.42
	Professional	56	2.60	0.59
	Total	300	2.76	0.45

The table 19 concluded that the mean value of Below 10th qualified father's student is 3.00 whereas the mean value of UG is 2.72, the mean value of PG is 2.77 and the mean value of professional is 2.60. The result inferred that the mean value of Below 10th qualified father's student is high compare to others.

Table 20: F-ratio towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of father among higher secondary school students.

Source of variance	df	Sum square	Mean square	F	Remarks
Between Group	3	4.54	1.515	7.97	Not Significant
With in group	296	56.176	0.190		

The table 20 concluded that the calculated value of "F" (7.97) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.65, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of father among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 9:

There will be a significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of mother among higher secondary school students.

Table 21: Means score difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of mother among higher secondary school students.

Variable	Educational Qualification of Mother	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Below 10 th	65	3.00	0.00
	UG	122	2.66	0.47
	PG	56	3.00	0.00
	Professional	57	2.45	0.599
	Total	300	2.76	0.45

The table 21 concluded that the mean value of Below 10th qualified mother's student is 3.00 whereas the mean value of UG is 266, the mean value of PG is 3.00 and the mean value of

professional is 2.45. The result inferred that the mean value of Below 10th qualified and PG qualified mother's student is high compare to others.

Table 22: F-ratio towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of mother among higher secondary school students.

Source of variance	df	Sum square	Mean square	F	Remarks
Between Group	3	13.35	4.45	27.81	Significant
With in group	296	47.36	0.160		

The table 22 concluded that the calculated value of "F" (27.81) is greater than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.65, the Null hypothesis is rejected .It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of mother among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 10:

There will be a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of father among higher secondary school students.

Table 23: Means score difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of father among higher secondary school students.

Variable	Occupation of Father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Daily Wagers	44	2.72	0.45
	Farmer	89	2.71	0.45
	Govt.Job	65	3.00	0.00
	Private	44	2.40	0.49
	Business	58	2.84	0.48
	Total	300	2.76	0.45

The table 23 concluded that the mean value of daily wagers' student is 2.72 whereas the mean value of Farmer is 2.71, the mean value of Govt. Job is 3.00, the mean value of Private is 2.40 and the mean value of Business is 2.84. The result inferred that the mean value of Government job father's student is high compare to others.

Table 24: F-ratio towards social intelligence between the occupation of father among higher secondary school students.

Source of variance	df	Sum square	Mean square	F	Remarks
Between Group	4	9.775	2.44	14.15	Significant
With in group	295	50.945	0.17		

The table 24 concluded that the calculated value of "F" (14.15) is greater than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is rejected .It is inferred from the above table

that there is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of father among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 11:

There will be a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of mother among higher secondary school students.

Table 25: Means score difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of mother among higher secondary school students.

Variable	Occupation of Mother	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Intelligence	Daily Wagers	55	2.76	0.42
	Farmer	65	2.61	0.49
	Govt.Job	44	3.00	0.00
	Private	25	2.48	0.50
	Business	13	3.00	0.00
	Home maker	98	2.78	0.48
	Total	300	2.76	0.45

The table 25 concluded that the mean value of daily wagers’ student is 2.76 whereas the mean value of Farmer is 2.61, the mean value of Govt.Job is 3.00, the mean value of Private is 2.48, the mean value of Business is 3.00 and the mean value of Home maker is 2.78. The result inferred that the mean value of Government job and business doing mother’s student is high compare to others.

Table 26: F-ratio towards social intelligence between the occupation of mother among higher secondary school students.

Source of variance	df	Sum square	Mean square	F	Remarks
Between Group	5	6.66	1.33	7.38	Significant
With in group	294	54.05	0.18		

The table 26 concluded that the calculated value of “F” (7.38) is greater than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 2.26, the Null hypothesis is rejected .It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of mother among higher secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS 12:

There will be a significant relationship between social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

Table 27: Correlation(r) value between social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

S.No	Variable	N	r- value	Sig.
1	Social Intelligence	300	-0.218	Significant At 0.05 level
2	Academic Achievement in English			

The table 27 concluded that the calculated r -value -0.218 is less than the tabulated r-value 0.811 at 0.05 level. Hence the correlation is not significant. The result inferred that there is no significant relationship between social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

3. Conclusion

- There is no significant difference towards social intelligence between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant difference towards achievement in English between medium of instruction among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference towards social intelligence between gender among higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant difference towards achievement in English between gender among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference towards social intelligence between location of the school among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference towards achievement in English between location of the school among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference towards social intelligence between the types of school among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of father among higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the educational qualification of mother among higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of father among higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant difference towards social intelligence between the occupation of mother among higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and achievement in English among higher secondary school students.

The investigator found that majority of higher secondary school students social intelligence is low, but the academic achievement is moderate to high. Then the correlation study reveals the relationship between the social intelligence and academic achievement is low. There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement. This study shows that students do not find healthy environment in schools for developing their social intelligence.

The schools fail to provide a proper environment to develop better relationship, positive behavior, social skills positive attitudes and good mental health in students.

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